

Transformer Inrush Mitigation Using Controlled Switching of a 500-kV Circuit Breaker

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Abstract—This paper presents post event analyses of three inrush events that caused relay misoperation. It then presents the results of an EMTP study that illustrates the degree to which different techniques can mitigate the transformer inrush transient and compares this to the predicted performance of closing resistors in an identical application. It demonstrates that controlled switching of a transformer adequately mitigates inrush transients.

I. INTRODUCTION

The traditional method of energizing a transformer has been through the random closing of the circuit breaker poles. Due to the stochastic nature of the application of system voltage on the transformer, the transformer's core can likely be driven into saturation. This can produce large inrush currents well above the rated current of the transformer, even approaching its short circuit rating. These currents have a high direct current component and are rich in second and third harmonics. Furthermore, they typically will not reach the steady-state transformer magnetizing current value for a number of seconds because of weak damping of the power system. The inrush currents can cause transformer damage resulting from the magnetic forces of these currents. Additionally, they can cause temporary harmonic overvoltages on the system and unwanted operation of protective devices including overcurrent and differential relays, and fuses, thus effecting power quality [1], [2], [3].

The inrush current of the transformer is a result of the saturation characteristic of the transformer's core. Power transformers are operated with the core flux near the bend in the saturation curve. When nominal core flux is applied to a core that is only moderately saturated, the core flux will be impressed upon the linear portion of the saturation curve. Thus, the sinusoidal variation in the core flux will produce large asymmetries in the induced current [1]. Since the core flux is the integral of the applied voltage, a reduction in the applied sinusoidal voltage will lead directly to a reduction in the core flux. It follows that by lowering the core flux it will

result in lower inrush currents. Historically, pre-insertion or closing resistors in circuit breakers have been able to take advantage of this relationship by initially reducing the voltage applied to the transformer, thereby mitigating the inrush transient [2].

Another more modern method to reduce transformer inrush currents is through the use of a controlled switching strategy. Without considering the effects of residual flux stored in the transformer core and assuming there is no magnetic coupling between the phases of the transformer, the optimal time to energize a transformer is when the system voltage is at a peak. From Faraday's law, this corresponds to a zero crossing of the induced sinusoid of the core flux that makes the flux symmetrical and produces a minimal inrush. For transformers with coupled phases, such as three phase transformers or single phase transformers with delta connections, the closing of the first phase on voltage peak will induce a flux into the other two phases. To minimize the core flux in the other two phases these should be energized 90 electrical degrees from the first phase. At this point the prospective core flux will be approximately equal to the flux induced by the system voltage and the inrush current will be minimized [4].

While controlled switching is not a recent innovation, it was originally proposed in the 1960's, the state of technology has recently advanced to the point where it is possible [1]. For controlled switching to be practical, circuit breakers and the controllers themselves must be reliable and robust enough to produce results within a tolerance of ± 1 milliseconds [5] in all usual service conditions [4]. Modern SF₆ and vacuum switching devices and their drive mechanisms have designs with reduced internal parts and are, mechanically speaking, simpler and more reliable than their predecessors. Additionally, the drives are more predictable in their ability to switch power system currents and have a rate of change of dielectric strength that makes controlled switching more feasible than with previous generations of circuit breakers [4]. With the introduction of modern microprocessor based

technology, control devices could easily account for variations in temperature and control voltage which affect the speed of the mechanism. Additionally these devices now routinely exist in the harsh electromagnetic environment of a substation.

II. PIN HOOK SUBSTATION PROJECT

In 2000, Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA) began preliminary work to expand a 161-kV substation to integrate it into the 500-kV power system. The station is Pin Hook, TN 500-kV Substation. Because of site development issues at the existing site, 500-kV gas insulated switchgear (GIS) became the preferred option.

The 500-kV GIS is configured in a three position ring. There are two transmission line terminals and one 500/161/26.4-kV transformer terminal. The transformer bank is comprised of three single phase transformers externally connected in a grounded wye-wye-delta configuration. There is a fourth transformer which can be utilized as a spare.

Since TVA had limited experience with GIS, and no experience with GIS based around single pressure, puffer circuit breakers, this requirement provided the ability to reconsider some of the historical choices made in equipment application. One such choice was the use of closing resistors on 500-kV circuit breakers. For the 500-kV GIS, TVA chose to rely on controlled switching to mitigate inrush transients and switching surges and not to install closing resistors.

TVA has historically used closing resistors to mitigate transients in the 500-kV power system. This practice continued with the transition from air blast circuit breaker technology to SF₆ technology in the 1980's and is still a part of TVA's standard circuit breaker specifications. With the exception of two known instances of human error that damaged closing resistors, the closing resistors on modern gas circuit breakers have not adversely affected the in-service life of the circuit breaker fleet. Additionally, preventative and condition based maintenance for the closing resistor is performed at intervals consistent with other components in the circuit breaker interrupting chamber. However, even with a good maintenance record, the reliability of the closing resistor was a concern for maintenance of the GIS. If the need ever arose to perform corrective maintenance (CM) on the closing resistor, the space constraints and access issues of GIS as opposed to air-insulated switchgear was one of the primary concerns. Additionally, removing the resistor assembly decreased the complexity of the circuit breaker and could logically increase the expected reliability of the equipment itself. Failure of the electronic controller was considered a more reliable CM to perform considering many failures of equipment are just after invasive maintenance. Further, the state of the art of controlled switching was advanced enough, and there were enough installations of controlled switching in the United States and around the world, that the literature supported its use.

III. RELAY MISOPERATIONS

Commissioning of the controlled switching system was accomplished through online energization of the transformer bank. The first close attempt was made uncontrolled so that

the controller could learn the operating characteristic of the closing mechanism. As such, the transformer was energized the first time with no mitigation of the inrush transients. Moreover, field testing of the transformer usually drives the core into saturation and is often not demagnetized. Upon closing of the 500-kV circuit breaker, the transformer stayed in service for about 18 cycles and tripped the circuit breaker on differential relay operation. Figure 1 shows the osillography of this event. The peak current magnitude is roughly 8 kA peak. Calculations from the transformer manufacturer indicated that this was about the maximum value of inrush current that could occur for this transformer considering high residual flux and zero-voltage closing of the circuit breaker. Figure 2 confirms the breaker closed at the zero-voltage point. In the post-event investigation, a dissolved gas analysis indicated that the spare transformer, initially connected to C phase, had high levels of hydrogen gas. TVA connected the normal C phase unit to C phase while the spare was being investigated. Current transformer saturation was the most probable cause of the differential operation and relay settings were modified before the second attempt at energizing the transformer [6].

Figure 1. Transformer inrush current from first energization

Figure 2. Transformer inrush showing B-phase closing around voltage-zero.

For the second attempt, the transformer was energized again without the assistance of controlled switching. C-phase transformer had not been demagnetized. The inrush transient reached a peak similar to that of the first event. The transformer bank stayed energized; however, within seconds of the transformer energization, area capacitor banks on the 161-kV system tripped off line. The following day the transformer was energized without the aid of controlled switching, and area capacitor banks tripped again. Ground overcurrent relays caused the capacitor banks to trip offline. A harmonic analysis of these events oscillography data indicates that there were increases of voltage unbalance on the system which contained harmonics. The unbalanced harmonic voltages, especially the third harmonic, likely caused a flow of current in the neutral of the power system and operated the capacitor relays. Figure 3 shows the unbalance on the 500-kV system while Figure 4 shows the harmonic content of the line voltage.

Figure 3. 500-kV voltage unbalance after transformer energization

Figure 4. Harmonic content of 500-kV line voltage after transformer energization

IV. POST EVENT ANALYSIS

TVA used a consultant to assist in a post event analysis of the previous events and to better quantify the technical decision to use controlled closing over closing resistors. The power system at the 500-kV level and the 161-kV level were modeled in EMT. The Pin Hook transformer was represented with variable residual flux while other system transformers were modeled using a classical three winding transformer model with saturations. The analysis varied the residual flux in the transformer, the closing instant of the breaker, and the use of closing resistors to see the effects of

each on the inrush transient. For each run, the study investigated the magnitude of the inrush current; the degree to which the unbalanced 500-kV voltage was induced on the 161-kV system; and the neutral current in the capacitor banks.

A. Reference case

As a reference case, and to investigate how well the model preformed against event data, the Pin Hook transformer residual flux was set to a typical value and the breaker was modeled as closing at the voltage zero for the first pole to close [6]. The peak inrush transient as predicted by the computer model was around 6kA, which is consistent with the values from the three events. The plots of the RMS values of the bus voltages at the fundamental frequency and at the third harmonic show a clear unbalance between the phases that correlates directly to the values estimated on the 161-kV system. The study indicated that the neutral current in the capacitor bank is highly influenced by the third harmonic content of the voltage. Figure 5 shows that the expected second harmonic of the bus voltage and current quickly decays and third harmonic dominates after about 1 second and is slow to decay. During inrush, the Pin Hook transformer acts as a source for third harmonic currents. Since the third harmonic is a zero sequence harmonic, it flows through the ground connection onto the system and back to the Pin Hook transformer through other neutral connections in the area. This well explains the tripping of area capacitor banks subsequent to the latter two inrush events. Additionally, the predicted decaying second harmonic and increasing third harmonic is consistent with the two inrush events as illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 5. Harmonic content of the 161-kV bus voltage

Figure 6. Transformer inrush current from first energization

B. Closing resistors

Two values of closing resistors were investigated to show to what degree they could mitigate the inrush transients. Both resistors perform exceptionally well in damping the inrush current to less than 1000 amps. Additionally, the neutral currents in the capacitor banks are below the pick-up setting of the relays.

C. Controlled closing voltage peaks

Closing the circuit breaker at voltage peaks with a typical residual flux in the bank limits the inrush to about a third of its uncontrolled value. However, this still allows for flows of third harmonic currents that could cause misoperations of the capacitor bank relays.

Figure 7. Transformer inrush showing optimal closing strategy

Figure 8. EMTF prediction of transformer inrush using optimal closing strategy

D. Controlled closing optimal method

The optimal closing method as described in [4] was studied for its effect on the inrush transient. This method closes one phase on a voltage peak and then follows with a simultaneous close of the other two phases 90 electrical degrees later. Assuming an unknown residual flux in the transformer, the method has a lower inrush current than the uncontrolled case, but has the possibility to cause more 3rd harmonic neutral current to flow. This is especially the case if the breaker closes in on a positive voltage peak corresponding to a positive residual flux. This is from the summation of the applied flux moving in the positive direction adding to the residual flux already in the core [1]. In the case of a known

residual flux the first phase can be closed on the phase with no residual flux. This case very effectively limits the inrush transients and consequently the harmonic overvoltages and currents in the power system. Figure 7 shows an oscillograph trace of a recent transformer energization at the sister station to Pin Hook where controlled switching is also used. This strategy here has limited the inrush to less than 1000 amps. The analysis predicted inrush currents of about 1000 amps for this station as shown in Figure 8 [7].

V. CONCLUSIONS

- Uncontrolled switching of transformers can have system impacts away from the station being switched.
- Controlled switching can be applied to satisfactorily limit the inrush transient from energizing a transformer bank.
- Methods of controlled switching which take into account residual core flux are preferred to those that do not. However, controlled closing even without knowledge of residual flux limits the inrush transients.
- Without knowledge of core flux, closing resistors still limit the inrush transients and harmonic overvoltages better than controlled closing. With knowledge of residual flux, controlled closing is comparable to the use of closing resistors.

VI. REFERENCES

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